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ELECTROCOAGULATION-BASED REMOVAL OF COD AND HEAVY METALS FROM MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE LEACHATE: A CASE STUDY FROM BADULLA, SRI LANKA

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Landfill leachate is a major environmental concern worldwide due to its high concentration of organic matter, color, turbidity, and heavy metals. Untreated leachate can cause serious environmental and health issues. In Sri Lanka, leachate from the Badulla municipal dumping site exhibits similar hazardous characteristics, emphasizing the need for effective treatment. Electrocoagulation (EC) is widely applied globally for wastewater treatment, especially for removing Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) removal. However, its application in Sri Lanka for simultaneous removal of COD and metal ions has not been explored. This study evaluated the performance of EC on natural leachate collected from the Badulla site. Initial tests compared Fe (Ductile iron)/SS and Al/SS electrodes, with Fe/SS showing the highest removal efficiency at 3375 C/L, and it was selected for further experiments. Five samples (A–E) were collected, analyzed for COD, pH, turbidity, and metal ions, and combined into a composite sample (F). Only manganese (Mn) and iron (Fe) were detected; chromium (Cr) and cadmium (Cd) were absent. Experiments were conducted at various charge loadings (2025– 4050 C/L) to evaluate removal efficiency. Electrocoagulation of sample F at 2250 C/L achieved 66.35% COD and 36.04% Mn removal, while Fe/SS treatment of the discharge sample reached 81.82% COD and 100% Mn removal at 3375 C/L. Additional tests using Poly-aluminium Chloride (PAC) combined with EC showed that PAC alone did not remove COD, but adding PAC simultaneously during EC optimized COD removal to 54.44%. Minimal pH variation confirmed stable operating conditions. Minimal pH variation confirmed stable operating conditions. The study concludes that EC using Fe/SS electrodes, especially combined with PAC, offers an effective and sustainable approach for simultaneous removal of COD and metal (Mn and Fe) ions from landfill leachate.

Keywords: Electrocoagulation, Leachate treatment, COD removal, Manganese, Iron, PAC